

Spin-dependent electron transfer in electrochemically transparent van der Waals heterostructures for oxygen evolution reaction

Yang Li^{a,b,*}, Yan Wang^a, Andrew F. May^c, Mauro Fianchini^{d,e}, Chiara Biz^d, Saeyoung Oh^f, Yiru Zhu^a, Hu Young Jeong^f, Jieun Yang^g, Jose Gracia^d, Manish Chhowalla^{a,**}

^a Department of Materials Science and Metallurgy, University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB3 0FS, United Kingdom

^b Cambridge Graphene Centre, University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB3 0FA, United Kingdom

^c Materials Science and Technology Division, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, TN 37831, USA

^d MagnetoCat SL, Calle General Polavieja 9, Alicante 03012, Spain

^e Departamento de Química Física, Universidad de Alicante, Carretera San Vicente del Raspeig s/n, San Vicente del Raspeig, Alicante E-03080, Spain

^f Graduate School of Semiconductor Materials and Devices Engineering, Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology, Ulsan, Republic of Korea

^g College of Science, Kyung Hee University, Seoul, Republic of Korea

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ABSTRACT

Spin selective catalysis is an emerging approach for improving the thermodynamics and kinetics of reactions. The role of electron spins has been scarcely studied in catalytic reactions. One exception is the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) where strongly correlated metals and oxides are used as catalysts. In OER, spin alignment facilitates the transition of singlet state of the reactant to the triplet state of O₂. However, the influence of strong correlations on spin exchange mechanism and spin selective thermodynamics of most catalytic reactions remain unclear. Here we decouple the strongly correlated catalyst from the electrolyte to study spin exchange in two-dimensional (2D) magnetic iron germanium telluride (FGT) heterostructure. We demonstrate that transmission of spin and electrochemical information between the catalyst and the reactant can occur through quantum exchange interaction despite the catalyst of FGT being completely encapsulated by graphene or hexagonal boron nitride (hBN). The strong correlations in FGT that lead to enhanced spin exchange in OER are observed in graphene or hBN layers with thicknesses of up to 6 nm. We demonstrate that spin alignment in FGT leads to a lowering of thermodynamic barrier for adsorption of hydroxide ion and electron transfer to the catalyst. This results in up to fivefold enhancement in OER performance and improved kinetics. Our results provide clear evidence that transmission of both quantum mechanical and electrochemical information through quantum spin exchange interaction in FGT leads to an enhancement in catalytic performance.

1. Introduction

Catalytic reactions are controlled by two fundamental parameters: energy and angular momentum of reactants [1]. The conservation of the total angular momentum results in spin selectivity of reactions, where total spin of reactants is identical to that of products. If the transformation of reactants into products requires spin state transition, the reaction is forbidden or has high energy barrier. Spin-dependent electron transfer has been widely studied for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) [2–6]. In OER, the ground spin state of the reactant (OH[•]) in alkaline electrolytes is a singlet without unpaired electrons, whereas the

ground spin state of the O₂ product is a triplet with two unpaired electrons. The number of 3d electrons in OER catalysts occupying the e_g orbital near the Fermi level determines the spin states of cations and can affect the adsorption and desorption of oxygen species in OER [7–11]. As a result, OER occurs through spin-dependent electron transfer at the interface between reactants and catalysts.

The diffusion of spin-polarized electron decays exponentially with distance due to the quantum spin scattering and spin filtering effects [12–14]. External magnetic field can align magnetic domains in magnetic materials [15–17], which enhances the spin polarization and facilitates the transfer of spin-dependent electrons. It has been

* Corresponding author at: Department of Materials Science and Metallurgy, University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB3 0FS, United Kingdom.

** Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: y1539@cam.ac.uk (Y. Li), mc209@cam.ac.uk (M. Chhowalla).

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demonstrated that tuning the spin state of 3d transition metal-based catalysts [10,18,19] or application of external magnetic fields [15,16,20–26] affects the OER activity. While the theory of quantum spin exchange interaction in spin catalysts [27–30] has been widely applied to explain the OER activity [15], its validation through direct experimental evidence of spin-dependent electron transfer remains elusive. This challenge arises from the difficulty in isolating electron transfer from mass transport in catalytic reactions, primarily due to the intimate contact between catalysts and reactants.

To delve into spin-dependent electron transfer mechanism within OER, we utilise two-dimensional (2D) vertical van der Waals heterostructures as catalysts for OER. Specifically, we employ 2D Fe_3GeTe_2 (FGT) as the catalyst and a thin layer of either graphene or hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) on top as a non-magnetic spacer to separate the catalysts from the reactants. Our results indicate that graphene and hBN exhibit electrochemical transparency below a critical thickness. Moreover, enhanced OER current observed after spin alignment in 2D FGT

catalysts suggests quantum spin exchange interaction.

2. Results and discussions

Thin FGT flakes (> 10 -layers) were prepared by mechanical exfoliation of bulk crystals in a glove box ($\text{O}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O} < 0.1$ ppm) and examined by high resolution scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM, Fig. 1a). The corresponding elemental mapping from typical flake is shown in Figure S1 and the atomic structure is shown in Fig. 1b. Each FGT unit has a thickness of five atomic layers. There are two types of Fe atoms with different coordination environments, Fe^{3+} (Fe_I) and Fe^{2+} (Fe_{II}). The middle of the 2D FGT is a Fe_{II} -Ge layer, sandwiched by bottom and top Fe_I layers. The surfaces of Fe_I layers are covered by Te. The hexagonal 2D FGT is metallic (Figure S2) which provides itinerant electron spin states. The temperature-dependent anisotropic magnetization $M(T)$ in Fig. 1c reveals ferromagnetic character for FGT below T_c (210 K) and the magnetic easy-axis is the c -direction. Fig. 1d shows the

Fig. 1. Structure and magnetic properties characterization of Fe_3GeTe_2 (FGT). (a) Atomic-resolution high-angle annular dark field (HAADF) STEM image of FGT. Scale bar, 1 nm. (b) The dashed rectangular box denotes the crystal unit cell with $a = 3.991$ Å and $c = 16.33$ Å. Fe atoms occupy two different positions in the crystal structure. (c) Field cooling magnetization as a function of the temperature for FGT in a magnetic field (H_{app}) of 0.1 T perpendicular and parallel to the c -axis. The ferromagnetic order in FGT is below approximately 210 K and FGT has a strong easy-axis anisotropy. (d) Total electron yield signals on the $\text{Fe } L_3$ and L_2 edges in FGT recorded with left and right circularly polarized x-ray, denoted with σ^+ and σ^- , respectively. X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) signal $\Delta\sigma = \sigma^+ - \sigma^-$. The shaded areas illustrate the integrals over the XMCD signals at the L_3 and L_2 edges, respectively.

x-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) spectra of encapsulated FGT in which red and blue lines are the measured total electron yield signals using left and right circularly polarized x-rays and the black line is their difference. The spectra are divided into the Fe L_3 ($2p_{3/2}$) and L_2 ($2p_{1/2}$) edges due to the large $2p$ core spin-orbit coupling energy. The integration value over the L_3 edge and entire $L_{3,2}$ edges in Fig. 1d shaded area have equal sign. This suggests parallel alignment of spin and orbital moments, indicating a more than half-full $3d$ electron configuration is dominant in the valence of Fe ions, i.e., Fe^{2+} ($3d^6$) [31,32].

We used exfoliated graphene and hBN flakes with varying thicknesses to encapsulate FGT and realize vertical heterostructures by dry transfer method [33] (see details in Methods) to produce clean and defect-free interface – optical microscopy image and Raman spectra of the heterostructure were shown in Fig. 2a and Figure S3, respectively. The spin-dependent electron transfer mechanism in the heterostructures can be unveiled through magneto-transport measurements with the application of a magnetic field in Fig. 2b and OER measurements using microelectrochemical cells in Fig. 2d. The microelectrochemical cells were lithographically patterned so that only a well-defined area on the basal plane of the 2D heterostructure was exposed to the electrolyte. The reactants in the electrolyte (potassium hydroxide, KOH) are directly in contact with only the top layer (either graphene or hBN) of the heterostructure.

2.1. Catalytic electron transfer in graphene/ Fe_3GeTe_2 (FGT) heterostructure

For graphene/FGT heterostructure devices, the transverse resistance (R_{xy}) was measured in Hall bar devices such as the one shown in Fig. 2a. The relation between R_{xy} and the applied magnetic field ($\mu_0 H$) is given by $R_{xy} = R_{\text{Hall}} + R_{\text{AHE}} = R_0 \mu_0 H + R_s M_z$, where R_{xy} is composed of a linear Hall resistance (R_{Hall}) and an anomalous Hall resistance (R_{AHE}). $\mu_0 H$ is the applied out-of-plane magnetic field, and M_z is the magnetic moment perpendicular to the sample surface. As graphene/FGT is electrically conductive, R_{Hall} is negligible compared with R_{AHE} in the magnetic field range of interest.

When a charge current (I_x) in graphene flows parallel to the graphene/FGT interface, it is partially converted to a spin current via spin-dependent interface scattering – giving rise to transverse spin-polarized current (I_y) via the inverse spin-Hall effect in Fig. 2b. The transverse spin-polarized current gives rise to the observed anomalous Hall resistance. Thickness-dependent hysteresis in Hall resistance was observed in graphene/FGT (Fig. 2c). That is, the width of hysteresis loop reduced with increasing thickness of graphene and disappeared at a thickness of 8 nm. When the graphene thickness is increased, Hall resistance becomes more linear with applied magnetic field, indicating that the transverse spin-polarized current reduces. Investigation of magneto-transport shows that the graphene/FGT heterostructures generate spin-polarized current which is dependent on the thickness of the non-

Fig. 2. Electrical transport and catalytic characterization of graphene/FGT heterostructures. (a) Optical image of a lithographically patterned microelectrochemical cell device with schematic of electrical transport measurement set-up. Scale bar, 10 μm . (b) The schematics of the current flow path and spin-dependent scattering in the graphene/FGT heterostructure. (c) Transverse resistance (R_{xy}) of graphene/FGT as a function of thickness of graphene. (d) The schematic of a microelectrochemical cell OER measurement set-up. The applied magnetic field is around 360 mT (measured by a gaussmeter). (e) Polarization curves (10 mV s^{-1}) in 1 M KOH ($\text{pH} \approx 14$) for graphene/FGT at two different spin polarization states, graphene thickness = 4.7 nm, FGT thickness = 11.5 nm. Insets are Tafel plots. (f) OER current density of graphene/FGT as a function of graphene thickness at potential of 1.7 V versus RHE at two different spin polarization states.

magnetic graphene layer.

We investigated catalytic activity of graphene/FGT heterostructure in KOH electrolyte by linear sweep voltammetry measurements. An out-of-plane magnetic field was applied to the microelectrochemical cells (Fig. 2d) to tune the spin polarization of catalysts from a pristine state to an enhanced spin-polarized state. OER current from graphene/FGT heterostructure is shown in Fig. 2e. For reference, the OER activity from pristine graphene without FGT layer in the presence and absence of magnetic fields were also measured and shown in Figure S4. We found that the OER activity in pure graphene was at least two orders of magnitude smaller than in graphene/FGT heterostructures. Raman spectra of graphene layer in graphene/FGT heterostructure before OER and after OER measurements shown in Figure S5 reveal that graphene layer remains unchanged. The results in Fig. 2e suggest that FGT can catalytically evolve oxygen even though it is encapsulated by graphene. This suggests that the heterostructure is catalytically active for the OER and that graphene is electrochemically transparent to allow the reaction to proceed.

Moreover, as depicted in Fig. 2e, the OER current is almost twice as large in the enhanced state – that is when the spins are polarized with saturation magnetic field – compared to the pristine state when the spins are randomly aligned in FGT. In the enhanced spin-polarized state, the spin conduction channels selectively enhance quantum spin exchange interaction between parallel spin-oriented electrons from reactants and FGT during the OER, which facilitates the spin-polarized electron transfer for triplet O_2 evolution [34]. Insights into the kinetics of OER can be obtained from Tafel plots shown in the inset of Fig. 2e. Tafel slope decreased slightly from 66.8 mV dec^{-1} to 57.6 mV dec^{-1} in the

enhanced state. The reduction of Tafel slope indicates that OER can be accelerated by improving spin polarization.

In addition, we quantified the length over which electrochemical transparency from reactant in the electrolyte was transmitted through the top graphene layer in the graphene/FGT heterostructure. Fig. 2f shows the OER current density with varying thickness of graphene (see Figure S6 for more details). The current density in both pristine and enhanced states decreased dramatically above a thickness of 6 nm for graphene, consistent with magneto-transport measurements in Fig. 2c, which show that electron transfer in OER is dominated by spin-dependent scattering. The observed trends, where OER current increases with spin polarisation in FGT layer and experiences an exponential decrease with the thickness of the graphene layer, suggest that the quantum spin exchange effect plays an important role in the performance of OER.

2.2. Catalytic electron transfer in hBN/Fe₃GeTe₂ (FGT) heterostructure

In contrast to semi-metallic graphene where electrons from reactants can reach the graphene/FGT interface via conduction, hBN is an insulator and therefore any electron transfer must occur via tunnelling. To investigate the electron transfer limit, we measured current-bias voltage (I - V_b) curves from FGT/hBN/FGT tunnel junction devices (inset of Fig. 3a) to characterize the tunnelling effect in hBN layer. Measured current shows nonlinear dependence on applied bias voltages in Fig. 3a-c and Figure S7. The current arises from quantum mechanical tunnelling of electrons across the thin insulating barrier between two conducting materials. The magnitude of the tunnel current is dependent on the

Fig. 3. Electrical transport and catalytic characterization of hBN/FGT heterostructures. (a)–(c) I - V_b characteristic curves measured at different temperatures for FGT/hBN/FGT with different thicknesses of hBN. Inset of (a) shows a schematic of the FGT/hBN/FGT vertical junction and related spin-dependent tunnelling across the interface. (d) Hall resistance (R_{xy}) as a function of temperature obtained in hBN encapsulated FGT. (e) Polarization curves (10 mV s^{-1}) in 1 M KOH (pH ≈ 14) for hBN/FGT at two different spin polarization states, hBN thickness = 5.8 nm, FGT thickness = 10.7 nm. Insets are Tafel plots. (f) OER current density of hBN/FGT as a function of hBN thickness at potential of 1.7 V versus RHE at two different spin polarization states.

width and height of the barrier, which is the thickness of hBN. When the thickness was increased to 9.3 nm, the current decreased by approximately six orders of magnitude compared to when the hBN thickness was less than 3.5 nm. Also, the measured current was independent of temperature (10 – 300 K), which means that the quantum mechanical electron tunnelling is a dominant transport mechanism in FGT/hBN/FGT heterostructure.

The Hall resistance (R_{xy}) as a function of the applied out-of-plane magnetic field at different temperatures is shown in Fig. 3d. The nearly square R_{xy} hysteresis loops of FGT encapsulated by hBN indicate that the reversal of the magnetic moment in FGT occurs through coherent rotation of a single domain and the out-of-plane direction is the magnetic easy-axis of FGT. The spin-dependent electron transfer in FGT/hBN/FGT tunnel junction is determined by the spin transparency at the ferromagnetic and non-magnetic interface [35]. When electrons tunnel through the insulating hBN, the asymmetry in the spin-dependent density of states causes the majority spins to easily tunnel across the barrier while blocking the minority ones at the interface, which increases the spin current [36]. The tunnelling magnetoresistance (MR) ratio ($R_{AP} - R_P$)/ R_P variation in the spin-valve device configuration of magnetic tunnel junctions by changing an applied out-of-plane magnetic field can be used to monitor the spin current (R_P and R_{AP} indicate the MR in the parallel and antiparallel spin configuration of the FGT). Figure S8 shows that the magnetic field responses of the tunnelling MR exhibit typical spin-valve characteristics with well-defined bistable MR states of R_P and R_{AP} [35,37,38]. The spin polarization of the FGT in the tunnel junction depends on the thickness of hBN, which can be characterized by a spin injection and diffusion model [39]. This model exhibits an exponential decay described by e^{-d/l_s} , where d is the thickness of hBN, and l_s is the spin diffusion length.

Similar to graphene/FGT heterostructures, OER from hBN/FGT heterostructure and pristine hBN layer without FGT layer was measured and shown in Fig. 3e and Figure S9, respectively. We found that the OER current in hBN/FGT heterostructure was at least four orders of magnitude larger than pristine hBN. Raman spectra in Figure S10 confirm that hBN layer remains unchanged after OER. Hence, the catalytic activity of the hBN/FGT heterostructure in the OER suggests that hBN exhibits electrochemical transparency. Furthermore, the OER current is improved up to threefold in the enhanced state compared to its pristine state in Fig. 3e. The Tafel slopes exhibited a reduction by half, decreasing from 199.3 mV dec⁻¹ to 96.6 mV dec⁻¹ in the enhanced spin-polarized state. The higher magnitude of OER current improvement associated with hBN/FGT could be due to the more effective spin filtering at the interface compared to graphene/FGT because of the large band gap of hBN. Fig. 3f quantifies the dependence of OER catalytic activity in the hBN/FGT heterostructure on the thickness of the hBN layer (see Figure S11 for more details). The current density decreased with increasing thickness of hBN, and became negligible above a thickness of 6 nm, which was similar to the trend of tunnelling current and spin polarization decay with thickness of hBN in the FGT/hBN/FGT tunnel junctions. This indicates that electron transfer in OER with hBN/FGT as catalyst is dominated by spin-dependent quantum mechanical tunnelling.

2.3. Catalytic electron transfer in room temperature ferromagnetic Fe₃GeTe₂ (FGT5)/graphene heterostructure

Fe₃GeTe₂ (FGT) at room temperature is paramagnetic with disordered magnetic domains but can have locally ferromagnetic spin channels for fast electronic transitions. An applied magnetic field imbalances the density of spin-up and spin-down electrons, and modifies the spin polarization of the electrons in FGT. When the FGT is in ferromagnetic state, one spin-type electron is dominant and has remanent magnetization. To elevate the Curie temperature (T_C) of FGT, a common approach is to increase the iron density to achieve an iron-rich FGT, e.g. Fe₅GeTe₂ (FGT5). FGT5 has a similar crystal structure to FGT (Figure S12a) with

the exception that the Fe atoms in FGT5 occupy three inequivalent sites [40]. Temperature dependent magnetization measurements indicate T_C is 296 K in Figure S12b. FGT5 heterostructures with three different types of non-magnetic 2D materials (graphene, hBN and MoS₂) were fabricated using the same method as FGT samples (see Method for details). The magneto-transport properties of FGT5 are shown in Fig. 4a. The R_{xy} at zero magnetic field stays up to 295 K, signifying spontaneous magnetization. The results indicate FGT5 has room temperature ferromagnetism and the spin polarization in Fe sites remains after applying magnetic fields.

The OER catalytic properties of graphene/FGT5, MoS₂/FGT5 and hBN/FGT5 in 1 M KOH are shown in Fig. 4b-d. The OER current for all the FGT5 heterostructures in the enhanced state was improved by up to 5 times compared to its pristine state. Interestingly, when the applied magnetic field was removed, the improved OER current did not drop to the level of pristine state, which we refer to as the remanent state. The results indicate that the spin polarization from the remanent magnetization in FGT5 contributes to OER enhancement. We also investigated the top layer thickness dependence of OER in the FGT5 heterostructures and the results are shown in Figure S13-S15. The OER current density in FGT5 heterostructures at different thicknesses of graphene, MoS₂ and hBN shows similar trends as FGT heterostructures. In addition, most bulk catalysts for OER that are composed of ferromagnetic mixed-metal oxides or metals exhibit a linear correlation between the enhancement of OER current and their mass magnetization [21]. In contrast, as shown in Figure S16, van der Waals heterostructures as spin catalysts have a more significant enhancement in OER current than the bulk catalysts. This suggests that van der Waals heterostructure is more efficient to manipulate spins.

From our experimental results of magneto-transport and OER catalytic measurements, the non-magnetic top layer in the heterostructure between the reactants and catalysts can increase spin-dependent scattering at the interface and facilitate the spin filtering effect shown in Fig. 5a. The first electron transfer in OER is from reactant OH⁻ to the catalyst. OH⁻ does not have unpaired electrons, therefore the probability for providing a spin-up or spin-down electron is equal. Due to the quantum spin exchange interaction from catalyst, the first electron transfer step is spin-dependent and can efficiently bond adsorbed oxygen species optimally for catalytic activity [27]. Subsequently, deprotonation of the adsorbed hydroxyl radical (*OH) occurs with OH⁻ by extracting the only unpaired electron (e.g. spin-down) and formation of *O. The third electron transfer step follows the same mechanism as the first step and gives rise to *OOH with an unpaired spin-down electron. The paramagnetic *OOH intermediates undergo spin-selective pathway in Fig. 5b to form product oxygen with a triplet state.

3. Conclusion

Our findings provide compelling experimental evidence for the electrochemical transparency of spin polarization at the van der Waals heterostructure interface. We also demonstrate the pivotal role of quantum spin exchange interaction in governing spin-dependent electron transfer during OER activity. Moreover, we propose the utilization of microelectrochemical cells featuring van der Waals heterostructures as a promising experimental approach for investigating the intricate interplay between quantum correlations and thermodynamics in catalysts.

4. Methods

4.1. Growth of materials

Fe₃GeTe₂ crystals were grown from a flux using a melt of nominal composition Fe₆GeTe₉. The mixture was heated in a vacuum-sealed ampoule to 1180°C for 3 hours and then cooled at the rate of 3.3°C per hour to 750°C, at which temperature the crystals were removed from

Fig. 4. Electrical transport and catalytic characterization of room temperature ferromagnetic Fe₅GeTe₂ (FGT5) heterostructures. (a) Transverse resistance (R_{xy}) as a function of temperature obtained in FGT5. (b)-(d) Polarization curves (10 mV s^{-1}) in 1 M KOH (pH ≈ 14) for graphene/FGT5 (graphene thickness = 3.8 nm, FGT5 thickness = 10.9 nm), MoS₂/FGT5 (MoS₂ thickness = 2.5 nm, FGT5 thickness = 9.5 nm) and hBN/FGT5 (hBN thickness = 4.7 nm, FGT5 thickness = 9.3 nm) at three different spin polarization states. Remanent state is when the applied magnetic field is removed.

the flux using a centrifuge. The Fe₅GeTe₂ crystals were purchased from HQ Graphene.

4.2. Material characterization

Raman spectroscopy measurements were performed at room temperature with a laser excitation at 532 nm focused through a $\times 100$ objective lens. The spectra were taken at an incident laser power of below $50 \mu\text{W}$, which was sufficiently low to avoid any damage to the sample.

The cross-sectional TEM specimens were prepared using a focused ion beam (FEI Helios NanoLab 450). STEM images of few layer FGT were taken at 200 keV using a FEI Titan3 G2 60–300 with a double-sided spherical aberration corrector. The probe convergence semi-angle was set to be approximately 25 mrad. The inner and outer angle ranges for HAADF-STEM imaging were 50–200 mrad.

The XMCD measurements were carried out in a total electron yield detection scheme at the beamline I06 at the Diamond Light Source. The sample was measured under $\sim 1 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar vacuum conditions. All measurements were carried out at a magnetic field of 0.5 T and a temperature of 147.89 K. The scans were made over an energy range of 695–745 eV to measure the Fe L_3 and L_2 edges.

4.3. Device fabrication

All heterostructures were assembled in a glovebox (argon atmosphere with O₂ and H₂O content kept below 0.1 parts per million) to avoid sample degradation. FGT and FGT5 flakes (> 10 -layers) were prepared by mechanical cleavage from bulk crystal onto SiO₂/Si substrate with prefabricated alignment markers. Thin graphene, hBN and MoS₂ flakes (thickness of 1–15 nm, confirmed by atomic force microscopy) were also prepared by mechanical cleavage from high purity

Fig. 5. Spin-dependent electron transfer in OER. (a) Schematic representation of spin filtering mechanism in reactant (OH^-)—non-magnetic 2D layer—magnetic 2D layer (FGT). The electrons from OH^- can transfer through the top non-magnetic layer to the Fe^{2+} site in FGT and spin asymmetry is increased by the non-magnetic layer. (b) OER mechanism in alkaline electrolytes include four-electron transfer steps: ① $OH^- \rightarrow *OH + e^-$; ② $*OH + OH^- \rightarrow *O + e^- + H_2O$; ③ $*O + OH^- \rightarrow *OOH + e^-$; ④ $*OOH + OH^- \rightarrow O_2 + e^- + H_2O$. The spin alignment in FGT makes the intermediate oxygen species have a fixed spin direction (e.g., spin-down, blue arrows).

crystals (purchased from HQ Graphene) and transferred onto FGT and FGT5 inside glovebox using a dry transfer system, which included micromanipulator, hot plate and optical microscope.

Hall bar devices were fabricated by electron beam lithography (EBL). A double-layer polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) resist was used to pattern the contacts with EBL. Before the contacts deposition for hBN or MoS_2 encapsulated devices, the contacts area with hBN or MoS_2 covered was etched using reactive ion etcher with PMMA mask. 5-nm-thick Ti and 70-nm-thick Au films were deposited by electron beam evaporation to define contacts.

The fabrication of on-chip microelectrochemical cell was based on the Hall bar device fabrication, the surface of SiO_2/Si substrate was covered with PMMA as a passive layer to avoid the short circuits among electrodes, and EBL was performed to open a window on the surface of PMMA, where the investigated region was exposed to participate in electrocatalytic reactions.

4.4. Electrical transport measurement

Transport measurements were performed in a cryogenic probe station (CRX-VF, Lakeshore) with up to 2 T magnetic field and the temperature range was from 10 to 300 K. A constant 100 nA a.c. current at around 17 Hz was applied with lock-in amplifiers for all the transport measurements.

4.5. Electrocatalytic measurement

Electrochemical measurements were conducted in a three-electrode system, in which Ag/AgCl electrode was used as the reference electrode (RE) and Pt wire was used as the counter electrode (CE). A probe-connected to outer Au pad with the flake was used as the working electrode (WE). 1 M KOH (pH \approx 14) solution was used as the electrolyte.

The measurements were carried out using a multistat 1480 potentiostat. The polarization curves were obtained by sweeping the potential of the working electrode from 0 to 850 mV versus the reference

electrode at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} to minimize capacitive currents. The magnetic field was applied by a series of N52 neodymium magnets. The Ag/AgCl reference electrode was calibrated using a RHE calibrated Hg/HgO electrode. The current measurement from the working electrode was in the range of 10^{-9} – 10^{-5} A. The current density is calculated by normalizing the current to the area of 2D flake exposed to the electrolyte.

Author contributions

M.C. conceived the idea, supervised the project, and prepared the manuscript. Y.L. fabricated the devices, performed the measurements, analyzed the results, and prepared the manuscript. Y.W. helped device fabrication, OER measurements, interpreted results and prepare the manuscript. A.F.M. performed $Fe_{2.9}GeTe_2$ growth and crystal magnetic characterization. S.O. and H.Y.J performed and analyzed the STEM measurements. Y.Z. assisted in MoS_2 based device preparation. M.F., C. B., J.G. performed theoretical calculations, and helped in the interpretation of the results. J.Y. interpreted results and prepared manuscript. All authors commented on the manuscript.

Supporting information

Materials characterization; extended electrical transport and electrochemical characterization of van der Waals heterostructure catalysts.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Chiara Biz: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Mauro Fianchini:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Yiru Zhu:** Resources, Data curation. **Saeyoung Oh:** Visualization, Data curation. **Hu Young Jeong:** Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Jose Gracia:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Jieun Yang:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Yang Li:**

Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Manish Chhowalla**: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Andrew F. May**: Resources. **Yan Wang**: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.mser.2024.100856](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mser.2024.100856).

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Yang Li received his PhD in Materials Science at the University of Cambridge in 2020. Then he joined the Cambridge Graphene Centre and 2DMD group as a research associate. His current research interests focus on fundamental study into “beyond MOSFET” electronic devices using 2D materials.

Yan Wang received her PhD in Materials Science at the University of Cambridge in 2021. She is a senior research associate at Department of Materials Science and research fellow at St John's College, University of Cambridge. Her research is dedicated to leveraging the fundamental advantage of atomically thin semiconductors to create ultra-low power electronic devices. This involves the development of high-quality electronic materials, designing innovative device structures and engineering the properties of these devices to improve their efficiency and performance.

Manish Chhowalla is the Goldsmiths' Professor of Materials Science at the University of Cambridge. His research interests are in the fundamental studies of atomically thin two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides. Prof. Chhowalla is a Fellow of the Royal Academy of Engineering (FREng), Materials Research Society, and Churchill College. He is now the Editor-in-Chief of MRS Energy & Sustainability. He has been on the Clarivate Highly Cited Researchers since 2016. Prior to Cambridge, he was a Professor at Rutgers University in NJ, USA.